

Logo Guidelines

“A logo is not just a mark – it’s the embodiment of an organization.
Logos are symbols, and symbols don’t explain; they identify.”

Paul Rand

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About the Guidelines

Logo guidelines are a set of rules that dictate how a logo should be used to ensure consistency and protect the brand's integrity. They provide clear instructions on logo placement, size, clear space, and different versions to use across various platforms, helping to maintain a consistent visual identity and build brand recognition.

About the Logo

The logo represents precisely the MULTIPULM mission and values clearly across cultures as it is:

- **Empowering & Supportive:** approachable geometry, lowercase typography
- **Evidence-Based & Credible:** clean, minimal, no unnecessary embellishment
- **Inclusive & Culturally Sensitive:** avoids clinical or Westernised medical symbols
- **Innovative & Accessible:** built for motion, modularity, mobile interfaces
- **Collaborative:** adaptable for use by partners in multiple regions

All key deliverables are naturally supported by the brand structure.

Versions and Use

Variations of the Logo

Horizontal Logo

Best for websites, formal usage (i.e. deliverable reports), email footers etc.

Stacked Logo

Ideal for square media, social icons, motion graphics, videos, event and promotional materials.

Wordmark

When the M mark appears too often in a document, or if it is used as an image frame, to avoid repetition.

Mark

Can be used as a profile picture, favicon, avatar and as an image frame.

The Brand's palette

The brand palette combines teal, coral, mint green, and dark grey for a balance of trust, energy, and clarity. Gradients may be used in digital and motion applications. Always ensure sufficient contrast for readability. Avoid neon tones or unapproved variations. Monochrome versions may be used for limited-colour contexts like print or embossing.

Gradient

Coral Red

HEX: #FF4323

PANTONE: ORANGE 021 C

Mint Green

HEX: #007E77

PANTONE: 7717 C

Charcoal Grey

HEX: #333333

PANTONE: 426 C

Coral Pink

#E58385

Teal

#45ADB4

Vivid Crimson

#EA2E39

PRIMARY

SECONDARY

Logo Font

Parkinsans font

A geometric sans-serif Google font that has a bold presence and friendly curves. The lowercase version communicates openness and user-friendliness.

Its balanced weight makes it suitable for use in both healthcare and tech contexts. The same typeface, but in a lighter style, is used for the tagline.

It is elegant and legible, and compatible across Latin alphabets. It supports Turkish, Serbian and Portuguese.

multipulm

**Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm
Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0**

Parkinsans Bold

Parkinsans Medium

Parkinsans Regular

Text Font

Inter font

Inter is a variable font family carefully crafted & designed for computer screens.

Inter features a tall x-height to aid in readability of mixed-case and lower-case text. Several OpenType features are provided as well, like contextual alternates that adjusts punctuation depending on the shape of surrounding glyphs.

It is elegant and legible, and compatible across Latin alphabets. It supports Turkish, Serbian and Portuguese.

multipulm

**Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn
Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0**

Inter Bold

Inter Medium

Inter Regular

Exclusion Zones

The clear space for the stacked logo

The safe area of the horizontal logo is typically 1x the size of the M element.

Exclusion Zones

The clear space for the stacked logo

The safe area of a logo, also known as the clear space, is an invisible buffer zone that should remain free of other design elements. This ensures that the logo remains legible, professional and impactful. The safe area for the stacked logo is determined by measuring the logo itself; 0.5x the size of that element is the main guideline.

Logo Application

Proper positioning examples

Use the official MULTIPULM logo in horizontal or stacked form. Maintain clear space around it and avoid distortion or colour changes. The “M” symbol may be used as a standalone icon or media frame in digital content. Use full-colour or white versions on solid backgrounds. Avoid busy imagery behind the logo and never modify its proportions or structure.

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proident in sit mollit in sunt do dolore.

**multi
pulm**

Smartphone-based
monitoring

brings specialist care

to resource-limited
communities

Accessible, integrated care for people with multiple chronic conditions in low & middle income countries (LMICs)

Chronic respiratory multimorbidity is rising worldwide, hitting LMICs hardest. MULTIPULM brings patient-centred digital care to Brazil, Serbia, and Türkiye, where unequal access and limited tools demand urgent, innovative solutions.

[How it works](#)

Key figures

€4.4m

Horizon Europe
project

48

months
(2025–2029)

18

partners from
10 countries

2,750

patients in clinical
validation

Reminders

Rules on logo use to keep in mind

DO NOT change the color.
Use only the colors in the palette.

DO NOT crop
the logo.

DO NOT add shadows
or effects.

DO NOT rotate
the logo.

DO NOT put over
another illustration.

DO NOT use tint
or opacity.

Reminders

Minimum size requirements

for web usage

450px / 96ppi

150px / 96ppi

200px / 96ppi

40px / 96ppi

for printing usage

12 cm / 300dpi

4 cm / 300dpi

5 cm / 300dpi

1 cm / 300dpi

About the Project

MULTIPULM is a project funded by the Horizon Europe programme that delivers integrated, digital-based interventions for patients with multiple chronic respiratory conditions in Brazil, Serbia and Turkey.

The project uses remote monitoring, local capacity building and scalable tools to reduce health inequalities in LMICs.

The visual identity must reflect this global ambition by presenting a flexible, inclusive and digitally native brand system.

Thank you!

For any clarification or custom requirements,
please do not hesitate to contact.

Future Needs

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